

RELEVANCE REVISITED: THE VERSES OF SHRIMAD BHAGAVAD GITA FOR MODERN STUDENTS

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Abstract-

The divine preachings of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita changed Arjuna's perception towards the battle, which was against his own kith and kins. He was able to visualize the divinity in objectives of that battle after getting enriched with the knowledge delivered by God Himself. Likewise, the precious preachings of the Gita contain the keys to unlock the mysteries of life and to erase the dilemma due to complexities of life. Previous researches and interpretations show that Shrimad Bhagavad Gita has the content of such power that can change the meanings of human life. It is fruitful for all at every stage of life. People get motivation, how to lead a life loaded with aims and objectives and perceive the secret behind their birth and the evolution of the universe. Generally, it is considered that the philosophy of the Gita is needed and heeded on by the senile generation. On the contrary these divine preachings are to be grasped ab initio i.e. from student life. But in present era, students are directly or indirectly motivated to focus on the education which can make them able to earn more and more money and getting rich economically. Youngsters seem to adopt the trend anticipated by Wordsworth- "The world is too much with us/ Getting and spending we lay waste our powers." It seems that the society has forgotten the true meaning of education. In the real sense we are not educating our students but we are only making them able to earn luxury and live their life aimlessly without considering that the luxury cannot be interpreted as happiness. But the question arises how to teach the students the real meaning of life. The answer lies in the universal preachings of The Gita. Present paper will delineate different verses of the Gita with the interpretation which can be helpful for students to understand how to be a better citizen of India, a country which is known for its culture and moral values.

Keywords- Shrimad Bhagavad Gita, Values, Education, Slokas, Enlightenment.

Introduction-

Several definitions of education has been interpreted since time immemorial. An elementary meaning of education is 'the process of learning'. Every nation is unlike to other nation in its culture and civilization but unfortunately, we Indians are following the education system of Europe at present. Like a face cream or a shampoo made for the people, living in cold regions according to their skin type and scalp, cannot be fruitful to the inhabitants of hot climate. Instead, it will harm their skin and scalp. Likewise, if we follow the education system devoid of Indian culture and tradition can never be beneficial for our students. India, a country which values morals and ethics in our daily life, lacks value-oriented education in our curriculum. It is the need of the hour to explore the ethical values of Shrimad Bhagavad Gita and vitalize the intellect of the students so that the modern students can understand the real value of education and can be able to apply it in their life accordingly.

When we look at our ancient education system, students were taught Vedas, Upanishads, Puranas etc. it shows that students were given value-oriented education and taught how to discipline their lives to get self-realization. They were asked to follow four Ashramas and were trained in values so that they could relish all four Ashramas in their lives successfully. That was called the authentic human life. But in present scenario,

students of today are seen blindly rushing towards materialism and employment seeking pleasure just to lead luxurious life. From the very beginning of their schooling, they are taught to follow western culture and gradually when they grow, they act like a machine being guided by modern technology and western culture. They are quite unknown towards rich treasure of Vedas or Upanishads. An invisible web of materialism has been created around our students which has covered them all around and there remains no path to escape. According to Swami Prabhupada,

“What is the problem of our lives? That we do not know. Modern education never gives enlightenment about the real problem of life. That is indicated in the Bhagavad-gita. Those who are educated and are advancing in knowledge should know what is the problem of life.” (165)

In modern era teenagers are living a frustrated life, knowing nothing about the goals or what they have to do in future. Being obsessed with luxuries and advancement of present age they have started ignoring practicality of life. Their one-sided understanding of life has marred the true essence of modernity. In other words, young generation of present age is getting morally and culturally dead. As time passes, they start understanding what they lack in their life. As it is said by Swami Ranganathananda,

“Machines never made mankind happy and never will make. He who is trying to make us believe this, will claim that happiness is in the Machine; but it is always in the mind. That man alone who is the lord of his mind can become happy, none else.” (46)

The appropriate appraisal of life can be understood only through value education which is not easy to communicate to our students without their own interest. Shrimad Bhagavad Gita which is the essence of Vedas and Upanishads can be taught to our students because it consists only 18 Chapters and 700 Verses. Besides it The Gita is in the form of conversation between Arjuna and Lord Krishna like a Guru and a disciple. So the preachings of the Gita will be quite helpful for our students to interpret the relevance of value education at modern times. Shri Aurobindo says,

“What we can do with profit is to seek in the Gita for the actual living truths it contains, apart from their metaphysical form, to extract from it what can help us or the world at large and to put it in the most natural vital form and expression we can find that will be suitable to the mentality and helpful to the spiritual needs of our present-day humanity.” (01)

True education does not mean a collection of luxuries or being able for employment; it is concerned with enlightenment of the self. In Kurukshetra, Arjuna was hesitating to show his valour before his family members. He curses his presence in the battlefield for the sake of kingdom but when Lord Krishna motivated him and explained the cause and purpose of the battle, he stood up again and fought the battle against his own loved ones. At that time Lord Krishna was a divine teacher and Arjuna represented the whole humanity as students. Written by Ved Vyasa and in the form of dialogue between Lord Krishna and Prince Arjuna, Shrimad Bhagavad Gita is an array of universal values and divinity. Eighteen Chapters of The Gita can be divided into three parts according to the preachings consisted in the Verses. First six Chapters deal with the delineation of Karma Yoga which can be considered as the primary teaching for a student. Next six Chapters deal with the guidance towards the path of devotion. The last six Chapters deals with the path of knowledge. These all three ways can lead a person to enlightenment or self-consciousness.

The success of a student lies upon his awareness regarding life, society and the whole world. A child gets birth not like a clean slate, instead according to The Gita, a human (Jeeva) gets birth with different potentials and different destinies according to his karmas in previous birth. His consciousness, his stamina and his karmas show him the path to lead a spiritual life and ultimate enlightenment. Because of the Maya of the supreme Lord, he forgets his destination. Too much attention to worldly possessions or artificial happiness cannot lead to salvation. One must renounce his attachments to unveil this cover of illusion or Maya. It is mentioned by Jayadayal Goyandaka,

“This Maya is not of an ordinary type like that employed by conjurers and demons; it is God’s own most wonderful power.... He who looks upon God alone....has renounced the sense of possession and attachment....It is only such devotees that are able to cross Maya.”(366)

The kernel of The Gita can help a student to know the ultimate truth of life and the correct way to lead to divinity. The indecisiveness of modern student ‘to be or not to be’ can be solved through the preachings of the Gita. There are several concepts and interpretations in the Gita which are helpful for students based on their modern surroundings and education system.

Slokas from the Gita relevant for the students-

There are a number of slokas from Shrimad Bhagavad Gita which have umpteen valuable gems to enlighten the potential of the students. A nonpareil example of a teacher and a disciple can be grasped in Arjuna as a dedicated student and Lord Krishna as a genuine teacher. Like a learner, Arjuna rendered out all his doubts regarding the battle and life before Lord Krishna one by one. Curiosity and desire to know more always prove to be beginning steps in the realm of knowledge. Without having the curiosity of things or without questioning,

none can be called a good student. Like a true teacher Lord Krishna stripped all his dubieties and revealed before him the path of truth. Shri Aurobindo says,

“There are three things in the Gita which are spiritually significant, the divine personality of the teacher, his characteristic relations with his disciple and the occasion of his teaching. The teacher is God himself descended into humanity; the disciple is the first, as we might say in modern language, the representative man of his age.....” (02)

Lord Krishna had the opportunity to opt Prince Duryodhana as a disciple and to apprise him the consequences of the battle. If this would have happened, he would have succeeded in stopping the battle which became the cause of thousands of deaths and bloodshed, but prince Duryodhana did not have the personality of a faithful student alike Prince Arjuna. Prince Arjuna followed all the instructions of his Guru Lord Krishna and won the battle for the sake of humanity. Now, modern students should learn from Arjuna that there should be indelible faith in teaching and experience of the Guru as well as stable devotion and enthusiasm towards learning.

The Slokas of the Gita has the nectar which the students must drink to grasp the realities of life. The state of dilemma, Prince Arjuna was in, is the state of every modern student which they undergo each and every minute so it is mandatory for the students to develop the capabilities so that they can differentiate between right and wrong. In Chapter 02, Sloka 14, as opted by Swami Mukundananda, it is said,

*“mātrā-sparśhās tu kaunteya śhītośhṇa-sukha-duḥkha-dāḥ
āgamāpāyino ’nityās tans-titikṣhasva bhārata” (2.14)*

It indicates that everything in this world is fragmentary, nothing is stable. Nobody should have concern of jovial surroundings or traumatic conditions. These sensory elements of the body cause different experience which come and go like the changing seasons. In this sense, students can grasp the principal of tolerance of sense perceptions. Its practice can assist them to eliminate aspirations which may create obstacles in their gaining knowledge. They can be able to face the unpleasant phases of life with courage because everything has an end and a beginning.

In Chapter 02, Sloka 48 Lord Krishna reveals,

*“yoga-sthaḥ kuru karmāṇi saṅgam tyaktvā dhanañjaya
siddhy-asiddhyoh samo bhūtvā samatvam yoga uchyate” (2.48)*

In this verse, there lies practical solution to predicaments of life. It clarifies that endeavours are in our approach, not the results and everyone should concentrate on doing the duty. In the reference to the students, the Sloka illustrates that they should work with patience. They should train their minds to remain calm at critical situations. They should renounce their attachments towards particular things. Their success or progress should not be limited only to the self-development but for the development of society. As Arjuna left his attachments towards his relatives and fought battle for the sake of truth, students should work hard according to their capability without being obsessed towards grades or employment. If they are able to hold their desires, they can achieve equanimity. Although the preachings of the Gita vitalize the monotonous life of human beings at every phase yet the delicate age of students should be guided by these precious thoughts strictly as the chances of deviation lie here at its apex. Lord Krishna teaches also how to avoid demerits from one’s own personality. He declares,

*“tri-vidham narakasyedaṁ dvāraṁ nāśhanam ātmanah
kāmaḥ krodhas tathā lobhas tasmād etat trayam tyajet” (21.16)*

Lust, greed and anger are the enemies of humanity. These are termed as the gateways to hell. Lust can distract a student from his path of truth and success. In the same way greed can mar the humanity in a student. Anger is also an enemy for the physical and mental health. By abandoning these three demerits from the character, a student can solve any problem which hinders his path of success. Rohan Kelkar and Dhananjay Mahajan realizes the involvement of positive vibes, the characteristics of every student,

“Student of today need two things one is awareness of doing their duties i.e. to study hard and build up their career as their “SWADHARMA” the way Arjuna did and secondly is inculcate the quality of FOCUS on the goal...” (157)

It is really wonderful that the book Gita is replete with universal practical wisdom to such extent that whole life can be relished smoothly through adopting these maxims. As these Satvic traits should be followed from the very beginning, the students are required to comprehend as well as mould its essence. In the verse 08 from the Chapter 03, work is declared the superior act for internal purification.

*“niyataṁ kuru karma tvam karma jyāyo hyakarmanah
śharīra-yātrāpi cha te na prasiddhyed akarmanah” (3.8)*

Everyone must be conscious about one’s duty. For students, hard work is a guarantee against downfall or failure. If they are devoted to their work, they are the true worshiper. The students should understand that if they are physically active and involve themselves in their studies and their prescribed Karma, they will definitely move towards success. To be active means leaving laziness and to maintain the physical health is

the only dharma and karma for every student. Likewise in the verse 26 from the Chapter 18, it is delineated that If they are sinless by heart in performing their duties and follow the path of Satya and Dharma like Arjuna, none on the earth can create hindrance in their endeavour. If they are endowed with qualities like enthusiasm, zeal and selflessness and became able to create balance between success and failure. In the Chapter 2 and Sloka 58, it is quoted-

*“yadā sanharate chāyam kūrmo ’ngānīva sarvaśhaḥ
indriyāṅindriyārthebhyas tasya prajñā pratiṣṭhitā” (2.58)*

Here it is declared that the power of self-control is necessary for everyone. If the students learn to follow detachment to worldly objects, they can focus on their sublime motives and ultimately can develop several attributes for succeeding in life. The example of tortoise is presented in the Sloka. As the tortoise has the ability to withdraw its limbs inside, students must learn to extract their conscience from sensory organs. Equanimity can be achieved only by following detachment from worldly pleasure. The following sloka from Chapter 02, is world famous quote to inspire human beings to be dutiful-

*“karmaṇy-evādhikāras te mā phaleṣhu kadāchana
mā karma-phala-hetur bhūr mā te saṅgo ’stvakarmaṇi” (2.47)*

It emphasises that everyone must focus on their actions and those action should be for the good cause, not about the fruits of his action. One should know one’s Swadharma and should act accordingly being detached to his actions. Every student must learn from the Sloka that results are not the sole target but the right action is primary for consummate success. The result depends on our efforts and finally becomes our destiny. After the hard work, the student should accept the outcomes whether expected or unexpected. He should be happy for his struggle he has faced during his journey. Dr. Ranjana Patidar opines,

“A sincere person tries to control the active senses by the mind and begins “Karma Yoga without attachment” is for more superior. One cannot even maintain the physical health without work; the body will be diseased or fall ill without work. So, this piece of advice, to follow the path of total self-surrender in hands of supreme power when one finds the path of knowledge and action difficult to follow, is worth accepting for mental and physical health.” (318)

In the verse fourth and fifth from Chapter 10, Lord Krishna elaborates human attributes. The source of all these qualities is the Lord himself. Here twenty emotions have been outlined which are root of the development of qualities in human beings. The dominance of the emotion formulates a person’s character. Every student should try to develop all these qualities to live a successful life with sublimity and to comprehend the supreme existence. These qualities are mandatory to maintain balance in the universe. The twenty qualities are, intelligence, proficiency, being confident and assured, being compassionate, being able to speak the truth, having control over senses, controlling negative thoughts in the mind, leaving distress, being balanced in happiness and miseries, having fear of God, being fearless at the same time in adverse circumstances, having the quality of nonviolence, equilibrium, satisfaction, following austerity, charity, to be confident whether it is fame or defame are the qualities which are bestowed on humanity by God and which every human being must try to possess. Just consider if every student inculcates most of these truths in his character, the future generation will emerge as superb human beings in real sense. Then ‘goodness’ will be the example to be followed continuously. As it is delivered in twenty first verse of third chapter-

*“yad yad ācharati śhreṣṭhas tat tad evetaro janah
sa yat pramāṇam kurute lokas tad anuvartate” (3.21)*

This Sloka illustrates that every great man has the responsibility to instil new standard for the new generation. And every rising generation has the duty to follow the footsteps of great men as well. The action of those great men contributes in augmentation of new things. This is the reason that students are provided the example of great people like Swami Vivekananda, Mahatma Gandhi, Radhakrishnan etc. to follow the line laid down by them whether it is for morality or for this material world. Swami Ranganathananda states,

“... These are consequences of the spiritual awareness of human beings. That is how great teachers work and great reform movements are born as a result of the inspiration derived from such great people. It is like watering the roots of the tree and not merely the branches and leaves.” (51)

Students must remember that they must work according to their situation, condition, time and their state in the society. Following anyone blindly cannot fulfil the purpose of life. Whatever duty God has bestowed on us, we should honestly try to fulfil for the sake of forthcoming generation to follow the footsteps left by us. For it, they will have to overcome lust, the root cause of vices. In fourth verse of chapter three Lord Krishna announces that at the early age, everybody should curb the desire of the senses-

*“tasmāt tvam indriyāṅyādau niyamyā bharatarṣhabha
pāpmānam prajahi hyenam jñāna-vijñāna-nāśhanam” (3.4)*

In present scenario, it can be seen among teenagers to develop the habit of smoking. If the student has the urge of smoking, he will remain agitated for cigarettes, while another student will remain dedicated towards achieving his motto. Such material desires easily demote the students and destroy the purpose and happiness of the soul. This sloka delineates that our mind is guided by our intellect. Our mind has so many distractions at a time, but our intellect restrains our attachment toward worldly things and moves us towards our aim. It is possible only when our intellect is guided by knowledge and right action. If we have the ability to control our mind, we can execute our ambitions. Thus, our intellects determine the destination that is fixed and unshakable and one can achieve higher levels of enlightenment. So, the student must have single aim to attain success without any selfish motives and delusions. In Chapter 02 Sloka 38, Lord Krishna reveals the secret of happy and robust life-

*“sukha-duḥkhe same kṛtvā lābhālābhau jayājayau
tato yuddhāya yujyasva naivam pāpam avāpsyasi” (2.38)*

The essence of the verses enhances our positive attitude even in adverse circumstances. Pleasure or pain, benefit or loss, victory or defeat both should be treated alike. The only sin is neglecting our duties. The message behind this sloka for student is to be the same in every situation. Most of the times students fall under depression because of failure in examination or job interviews. As a result, they commit suicide also. But they must understand that they are made only for the fulfilment of their prescribed duties. They should not worry about the consequences whether it is success or failure. It may be that they cannot get willing results but it is all because of their ignorance to their duties. Arjuna was fearful for fighting the battle but Lord Krishna taught him to be detached to victory or defeat. He should only focus on his duty to fight the battle for the betterment of society. His indifference towards the consequences of the battle will lead him to eternal peace.

Conclusion-

Shrimad Bhagavad Gita or ‘God’s Song’ is known worldwide for its educational aspects which were preached by God Himself. Lord Krishna persuaded Arjuna for his humanly duties but the universality of the message has made it relevant for one and all. Being filled with Vedic philosophical thoughts it simultaneously highlights the pros and cons of material life and enhances our inclination towards spirituality in real sense. The Gita elaborates different concepts, if interpreted correctly before students, their life can change to a great extent. Pravatti and Nivratti Marga, Gunas like Sattavic, Rajasic and Tamasic, concept of Maya, omnipotence of Time or Kala, Karma yoga etc. are the concepts which can be helpful for the students. From the educational perspective the Gita contains all the elements necessary for education system as well as for the students. The true education teaches student to be fearless, work according to his aim, leaving vices and to develop all the humanly qualities to be a better person. It teaches also how to deal with crucial situations and how to perform renunciation. For the cultivation of knowledge, intellect, wisdom, abilities etc. in human beings, it is mandatory to train them for their karmic and dharmic life from the very beginning of their student life to be ready to fight the battle of life. Sri Aurobindo has said,

“The Gita is therefore addressed to a fighter, a man of action, one whose duty in life is that of war and protection, war as a part of government for the protection of those who are excused from that duty.....for the protection of the weak and the oppressed and for the maintenance of right and justice in the world.” (13)

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